

Triterpenes from *Ajuga macrosperma* Wall.

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Ajuga macrosperma Wall. ex Benth syn. *A. repens* Roxb.¹ (Labiateae) is a bitter herb occurring scatterly in the waste hilly lands of Tripura. Earlier amino acids and fatty acids were reported² from the plant. Herein we report the isolation of β -sitosterol, betulinic acid and 3-*epi*-betulinic acid from the aerial parts of the plant. The acetate, lactone and bromo derivative of 3-*epi*-betulinic acid were also prepared.

Air-dried coarsely powdered aerial parts (2 kg) of *A. macrosperma* was Soxhletted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°). The petroleum ether extract on column chromatographic analysis over silica gel (mesh 60–120) afforded β -sitosterol from the petroleum ether-benzene (3 : 1) eluents. The benzene-chloroform (2 : 1) eluents yielded two compounds identified as 3-*epi*-betulinic acid (AJ-1, 1 g) and betulinic acid (AJ-2, 0.08 g) from the comparison of their spectral data with those of the authentic compounds³.

Compound AJ-1 (0.2 g) on refluxing with 98% formic acid (10 ml) for 5 h followed by usual work-up of the mixture gave a residue which on column purification with petroleum ether-benzene (5 : 1) afforded a solid, which on repeated crystallisations gave a lactone in granular crystals (0.13 g), m.p. 286°. The structure of the lactone was assigned as 3 α -formyloxy-18 α -oleanano-28,19 β -lactone (2a) : $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -30.2° (chloroform, *c* 0.2); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1765 (lactone C=O) and 1710 cm⁻¹ (aldehydic C=O); ¹H nmr (CDCl₃) δ 0.88 (9H, s), 0.92 (3H, s), 0.96 (6H, s), 1.04 (3H, s), 3.96 (1H, H-19), 4.64 (1H, t, *W*_{1/2} 6 Hz, H-3), 8.12 (1H, s, OHC-O-3); *m/z* (rel. int. %) 484 (M⁺, 1), 456 (3), 438 (100), 423 (29), 395 (57), 202 (57) and 189 (56). It may be noted that previous workers^{4,5} also obtained simi-

lar formyl lactone (2b) from betulinic acid on refluxing with formic acid.

A solution of AJ-1 (0.05g) in chloroform (5 ml) was brominated⁴ with a 5% solution of bromine in chloroform (1.5 ml) at room temperature by stirring for 2 h. The resultant yellow coloured solution was diluted with chloroform, washed successively with aqueous NaHSO₃ and water, dried, concentrated and chromatographed over silica gel. The elution with benzene-chloroform (6 : 1) mixture gave a residue, which on repeated crystallisations from benzene-chloroform afforded a bromo-acid (1b) as needle shaped crystals (0.02 g), m.p. 190°; $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -2.2° (chloroform, *c* 0.15); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3440 (OH) and 1700 cm⁻¹ (acid C=O), ¹H nmr (CDCl₃) δ 0.88 (6H, s), 0.94 (3H, s), 0.96 (6H, s), 3.38 (1H, t, *W*_{1/2} 5 Hz, H-3), 3.96 (2H, br s, H-30), 5.00 (1H, s, H-29), 5.12 (1H, s, H-29); *m/z* (rel. int.%) 536 (2), 534 (M⁺, 2.5), 469 (7), 437 (13), 409 (5), 391 (6), 189 (20), 175 (5), 81 (100) and 79 (46). 3-*epi*-Bromo acid (1c) was reported earlier^{4,6} from betulinic acid under similar treatment. This is the first report of the formyl lactone and bromo acid of 3-*epi*-betulinic acid.

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1a, R = H, α -OH; X = H
b R = β -H, α -OH; X = Br
c, R = α -H, β -OH; X = Br

2a; R = β -H, α -OCHO
b; R = α -H, β -OCHO